

FROM RESILIENCE TO ANTIFRAGILITY

Building urban mobility systems that grow stronger through disruption

AntifragiCity is an EU-funded initiative focused on creating **antifragile urban mobility systems** that don't just recover from disruption — they learn, adapt, improve, and grow stronger because of it.

We are creating a new urban mobility governance model that enables cities to:

Detect and monitor

(near) real-time stressors and disruptions

Assess

their impacts through simulation and predictive tools

Evaluate

the public acceptability of proposed mobility triage scenarios

Make informed decisions

to mitigate those impacts and improve performance

Engage with citizens

through participatory methods and co-creation

We combine data, innovation, and citizen engagement to improve urban resilience.

Continuous monitoring

Using KPIs and sensor data to detect stressors in real time

Disruption analysis

Characterising events using a structured event ontology

Rapid response

Supporting decisions with a mobility triage tool for short-term incidents

Long-term strategy

Using simulations and predictive analytics to design adaptive traffic systems

Citizen co-creation

Engaging the public through Citizens' Forums and Living Labs to ensure inclusive and actionable solutions

Our Pilots

Our approach will be tested in real-world scenarios across four European cities: Bratislava (Slovakia), Larissa (Greece), Odessa (Ukraine), and Thessaloniki (Greece), each with different urban mobility contexts and unique challenges.

Discover
our work

The Consortium

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